
Synthesis and Characterization of Fe₃O₄ Magnetite Nanoparticles Coated with Silica Nanoparticles

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Abstract Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have been successfully synthesized by modification of the preparation method of Fe₃O₄ nano-particles, which were prepared from Iron (III) Chloride hexahydrate FeCl₃.6H₂O, Ferrous Chloride FeCl₂.4H₂O, Ammonia Solution (NH₄OH) and silica nanoparticles. In this study, a new preparation of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles were reported. The characterization of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles coated with Silica nanoparticles is done by TEM, XRD and Spectrophotometer.

Keywords Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticle, Silica, Synthesis, Characterization.

Introduction

Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles and their dispersion in various media have been scientific and technologic [1-3], owing to their unique properties in a magnetic field. They are actively used in various industrial and medical applications. The magnetic fluids based on magnetite and mineral oils or organic solvents are conventionally synthesized by alkaline hydrolysis of ferrous and ferric salts. The magnetite obtained is stabilized by surfactants. Oleic acid is often used as a surfactant to form a waterproof shell around the magnetite particles since oleic acid has higher affinity to the surface of superfine magnetite compared to other surfactants. The treatment of magnetite by oleic acid is the most complex and important stage of the magnetic magnetite fluid preparation [4-8].

In conventional technique, to prepare magnetic fluids, an excess base (NH₄OH) is used to form magnetite precipitates and then oleic acid is added as surfactant by forming oleate directly after the complete crystallization of the magnetite precipitate. The main procedure begins with the co-precipitation of Fe (II) and Fe (III) ions with addition of excess concentrated NH₄OH. The sediment is then isolated by magnetic decantation and treated with oleic acid at heating. In that is to say an organic carrier liquid is added under intensive stirring. To obtain concentrated magnetic fluids, treated procedure such as phase separation and extraction of excess surfactant and solvent are often needed. In this paper, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are prepared in higher concentrated hydrophobic magnetite by adjusting the amount of ammonium hydroxide and oleic acid, and the time of oleic acid addition. The key to the success of making such a hydrophobic magnetite is to add an appropriate amount of ammonium hydroxide and oleic acid. Finally a solution has remained neutral and the magnetite precipitated. The oleic acid, as a reactant, was added immediately after the formation of magnetite crystal, simultaneously with the crystal growth. We posited that the oleic acid will efficiently coat the Fe₃O₄ crystal at the growth stage and will create a highly concentrated hydrophobic magnetite precipitated [9-13].

We characterized the magnetite precipitated in terms of its morphology, particle size, magnetite properties, structure, and hydrophobicity / hydrophilicity by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Spectrophotometer and Powder X- Ray Diffraction (XRD).

Experimental Work

Materials:

Iron (III) Chloride hexahydrate $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.0%, Ferrous Chloride $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98.0%, Ammonia Solution (NH_4OH), Ethyl Silicate and Ethanol were purchased from Sinopharm chemical reagent Co, Ltd, China. Physical parameters of Iron (III) Chloride hexahydrate $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.0%, Ferrous Chloride $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98.0%, Ammonia Solution (NH_4OH), Ethyl Silicate and Ethanol and Hydrochloric Acid (HCl) are reported in table 1 to 6.

Table 1: General Characteristics of Iron (III) Chloride hexahydrate $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Molecular formula	Iron (III) Chloride hexahydrate $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.0%
Appearance	Yellow- red crystal
Molecular weight	270.29
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table2: General Characteristics of Ferrous Chloride $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$,98.0%

Molecular formula	Ferrous Chloride $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98.0%
Appearance	Green Crystall
Molecular weight	198.82
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table 3: General Characteristics of Ammonia (NH_4OH)

Molecular formula	Ammonia (NH_4OH)
Appearance	liquid
Molecular weight	17.03
Concentration	25 – 28 %
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table 4: General Characteristics of Ethyl Silicate

Molecular formula	Ethyl Silicate ($\text{C}_8 \text{H}_{20} \text{O}_4 \text{Si}$)
Appearance	Liquid
Density 20 °C (g/ml)	0.932 – 0.936
Molecular weight	208.33
SiO_2	≥ 28.4 %
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table 5: General Characteristics of Ethanol

Molecular formula	Ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$) $\geq 99.7\%$
Appearance	Liquid
Density 20 °C (g/ml)	0.789 – 0.791
Molecular weight	46.07
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table 6: General Characteristics of Hydrochloric Acid (HCl)

Molecular formula	Hydrochloric Acid (HCl)
Appearance	liquid
Molecular weight	36 .5
Concentration	36 – 38 %
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Synthesis of magnetite Fe_3O_4 nanoparticle:

The magnetite was Synthesized by modification method as in the following procedure [14-19]: first , 5.8 g $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 2.2 g $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were dissolved in 200 ml deionized water under nitrogen gas with vigorous stirring at 90 °C for 30 minutes. Then, 7.5 ml of 25 wt% NH_4OH was added to the solution to get black precipitated. After that it was collected and washed with de-ionized water and pure ethanol three times. And last dried oven for 24 hours at 80 °C to obtained black powder.

Preparation of Silica nanoparticles Coated magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles:

First, 0.5 g of Fe₃O₄ powder was dispersed in mixture solvent of 25 mL ethanol and 5 mL deionized water by sonication for 15 mins. Then, 5 mL aqueous ammonia (NH₄OH). After stirring the mixture, 3.7 mL TEOS was added drop wise to the solution repaid stirring condition for 24 hours and temperature 30 °C under vigorous mechanical stirring. After that, Fe₃O₄ @SiO₂ precipitate was collected using a permanent magnet, and rinsed repeatedly with deionized water until the filter was neutral. And last Fe₃O₄ @SiO₂ particles were separated from solution by centrifugation at 10000 rpm and washed three times with deionized water and pure ethanol. The Synthesized Fe₃O₄ @SiO₂ particle suspension was dried in oven at 80 °C for 24 hours.

Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) Test

For TEM Test, a small amount of sample was dissolved in 3mL of deionized water in test tube and the solution was stirred by ultra-sonication. Then 10 µL sample was transferred to clean Copper Grid and kept dried for the TEM test. The TEM micrographs of samples were observed by CM 12 Philips Transmission Electron Microscope.

Spectroscopy Results

For Spectroscopy Results, a small amount of sample was put in a test tube and then dissolved in 3 mL ethanol or chloroform and it was stirred by ultra-sonication to make sure the sample was uniform. Finally, solution was transferred to cavity of spectrophotometer and spectra were recorded at 400 to 750 nm.

For XRD results, a small amount of powder sample was put in the XRD machine connected with computer. The result was recorded between intensity (KCPS) and Degree (2θ) shown in the figures (1 & 2).

Discussion

The Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle was synthesized by heating to 90 °C of Fe₃O₄ and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles coated oleic acid in powder form. Plates 1-13, TEM, show the top-view TEM images of the Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticle and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle coated oleic acid. X-ray diffraction spectra shows of Magnetite nanoparticles and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle coated oleic acid (Figure 1). Spectra shows of Magnetite nanoparticles and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle coated oleic acid respectively dispersed in ethanol (Figure 2 & 3).

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Plate 1: TEM of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles

Plate 2: TEM of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles

Plate 3: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

Plate 4: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

Plate 5: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

Plate 6: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

Plate 7: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

Plate 8: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

Plate 9: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Plate 10: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Plate 11: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Plate 12: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles

Plate 13: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles

Plate 14: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles

Plate 15: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles

Plate 16: TEM of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles

Figure 1: XRD for Fe_3O_4 Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles

Figure 2: Spectra for Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles

Figure 3: Spectra for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles coated with silica nanoparticles

References

1. Nabil Abdullah Noman Alkadasi, *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, **2014**, 30 (3),1173-1178.
2. Nabil Abdullah Noman Alkadasi, *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, **2014**, 30 (3), 1179-1182.
3. Mihajlović. G, Xiong P, and von Molnár S. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2005**, 87, 112502-1-3.
4. Etier M, Shvartsman VV, Gao Y, Landers J, Wende H & Lupascu DC, *Ferroelectrics*, Taylor & Francis, **2013**, [347]177-[355]185 .
5. Maiti R, Chakraborty M, *J Alloy and Compd.* **2008**, 458, 450–456.
6. Riyanto A, Listiawati D, Suharyadi E, Abraha dK. *Prosiding Pertemuan Ilmiah XXVI HFI Jateng & DIY, Purworejo*, **2012**, 14 April, 203-207.
7. Asuhan S, Wan HL, Zhao S, Deligeer W, Wu HY, Song L, Tegus O. *Ceramics Int.* **2012**, 38, 6579–6584.
8. Zhoua X, Shi Y, Rena L, Bao S, Han Y, Wu S, Zhang H, Zhong L, Zhang Q, *J Solid State Chem.* **2012**, 196, 138–144.
9. Wang B ,Wei Q, Qu S, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, **2013**, 8, 3786 – 3793.
10. Sun J, Zhou S, Hou P, Yang Y, Weng J, Li X, Li M., *J. Biomed Mater Res 80A*: **2007**, 333–341.
11. Jiang W, Yang HC, Yang SY, Horng HE, Hung JC, Chene YC, Hong CY, *J Mag. Mag. Mater.* **2004**, 283, 210–214.
12. Hu P, Zhang S, Wang H, Pan D, Tiana J, Tang Z, Volinsky AA, *J Alloy. Compd.* **2011**, 509, 2316–2319
13. JO Park, KY Rhee, SJ Park, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **2010**, 256, 6945–6950.
14. UR Rahman O, Mohapatra SC, Ahmad S, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, **2012**, 132, 196–202.
15. Mukherjee J, Ramkumar J, Chandramouleeswaran S, Shukla R, Tyagi AKJ. *Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, **2013**, 22 January.
16. Miyauchi M, Simmons TJ, Jianjun Miao, Gagner JE, Shriver ZH, Aich U, Dordick JS, and Linhardt R. *J ACS Appl. Mater. Int.* **2011**, 3, 1958–1964.
17. Wang LL, Jiang JS. *Nanoscale Res Lett* , **2009**, 4:1439–1446 .
18. Nowosielski R, Babilas R, *J Achievements in Mater. Manuf. Eng.* **2011**, 48/2, 153-160.
19. Astuti, Claudia G, Noraida, and Ramadhani M, *Makara J Sci*, August. **2013**, Vol. 17, No. 2, 58-62.

